

SUPERIORITY OF LANGUAGE ACQUISITION TO TRADITIONAL LEARNING

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Abstract: Many language learners and teachers heavily rely on grammar-based teaching when they learn any language. However, the process and results of this approach bring a lot of disappointments, eventually leading learners to become frustrated and almost lose their motivation and hope to engage with another language. The effective way lies in realizing how the brain works and using that innate ability to acquire languages without being overwhelmed. This thesis demonstrates how acquisition is superior to traditional learning methods and exactly how it works.

Keywords: Language Acquisition, Comprehensible Input, i+1 Theory, Grammar Translation Method, Multilingualism in Uzbekistan, Explicit vs. Implicit Learning, Flow State.

Аннотация: Многие изучающие языки и преподаватели при обучении любому языку в значительной степени полагаются на грамматический метод. Однако процесс и результаты такого подхода часто приносят разочарование; в конечном итоге учащиеся впадают в уныние и почти теряют мотивацию и надежду на освоение нового языка. Данный тезис демонстрирует, почему естественное усвоение языка превосходит традиционные методы обучения и как именно этот процесс работает.

Ключевые слова: усвоение языка, понятный ввод, теория i+1, грамматико-переводной метод, многоязычие в Узбекистане, явное и неявное обучение, состояние потока.

Annotatsiya: Ko'plab til o'rganuvchilar va o'qituvchilar har qanday tilni o'rganishda asosan grammatikaga asoslangan o'qitish uslubiga tayanadilar. Biroq, bu jarayon va uning natijalari ko'pincha ko'ngil qolishiga olib keladi; oqibatda o'rganuvchilar tushkunlikka tushib, boshqa tilni o'rganishga bo'lgan ishtiyoqi va umidini deyarli yo'qotadilar. Samarali yo'l – miya qanday ishlashini anglash va tushkunlikka tushmasdan tillarni o'zlashtirish uchun o'sha tug'ma qobiliyatdan foydalanishdir. Ushbu tezis tilni o'zlashtirish (acquisition) an'anaviy o'rganish usullaridan qanchalik ustun ekanligini va u qanday ishlashini ko'rsatib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: tilni o'zlashtirish, tushunarli kiritish usuli, i+1 nazariyasi, grammatika tarjima usuli, O'zbekistonda ko'p tillilik, aniq va yashirin o'rganish, oqim holati.

In the modern era, learning a second language comes with so many benefits that it has opened many doors for individuals who can use it properly and fluently. The advantages of learning more than one language encourage people in Uzbekistan to

become multilingual or at least bilingual, especially in these years. For example, Zakirova and Sharipova have stated how knowing more than one language can positively affect both the financial state and mental state of an individual (Zakirova & Rasulova, 2025).

Historically, language learners and teachers have used many traditional methods ranging from memorization to drills based on grammar. However, it has been proved as less effective in terms of becoming high level language user. Although acquisition is not as dominated as traditional grammar teaching or some other methods, it can truly develop both understanding and fluency.

Explicit knowledge has been seen as the only way to learn a foreign language. However, the brain is very good at guessing new meaning through context which happens most of the time when it encounters unknown words. But when we turn on conscious minds every time to learn new words, that process will be disrupted and as a result it prevents acquisition from happening. When a person loses consciousness and ego only then one can become truly immersed in what is being acquired. Csikszentmihalyi (1990) argues that during flow, “the sense of time is distorted,” which leads to a self that becomes “more complex” (p. 74).

There have been many failures when grammar teaching is applied, which is commonly used by both teachers and learners. The students who have practiced new words and grammar rules consciously still make mistakes when they use the most basic grammar forms in their speech and writing. Of course, even native speakers may make incorrect sentences, but it happens occasionally. That shows how limited conscious learning is.

We have learned our mother tongue through listening and interpreting the meanings of words we do not know yet and become fluent users of it. This is called acquisition differing from conscious learning. According to Chomsky, this process occurs in the brain whether we intend it or not. This is inevitable, not voluntary (Chomsky, 1980).

Stephen Krashen states that comprehensible input paves the way to great acquisition. Acquisition plays a huge role for a person to become fluent. When a person acquires a language instead of learning it the process of brain becomes natural and automatic (Krashen, 1985). The rules and words that are learned by studying can be acquired by comprehensible input. But this input should contain messages that are understandable, and one level beyond what a person can comprehend. This is called “i+1” in Stephan Krashen’s theory (Krashen, 1982).

It is proven to be the most effective approach to becoming a good language user. However, it is less known even among teachers and students who have been in this field for a long time. The evidence that is given in this thesis demonstrates how learning a language using a conscious mind can disrupt the natural ability of the brain to acquire what is unknown. To obtain the meanings of new words a person should get an excessive amount and proper level of comprehensible input. And finally, during the process of acquisition a sense of awareness should be turned off.

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